

WEAVERS' STRESSORS AS THE PREDICTORS OF ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE: A STUDY OF MADHUBANI DISTRICT OF NORTH BIHAR

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ABSTRACT

The present study is aimed at studying the weavers' stressors of occupational stress towards perceived organizational change with reference to weavers working in Madhubani district of North Bihar – a well – known district of North Bihar where different kinds of cotton cloths are being manufactured by hand loom. In the present study hundred weavers (N=100) from different locality of Madhubani district selected randomly. Data were collected through questionnaires individually. Having collected the data individual scores was summed up as per norms of scales for giving an appropriate statistical treatment. After analyzing the data, two stressors, viz., 'Powerlessness' and 'Low Status' of occupational stress index and one biographical variable 'income' as the stressors have been found to predict weavers' perceived reactions to organizational change. It is very interesting to note that only 19% of Madhubani weavers have shown their reactions towards the acceptability of perceived organizational change, although, most of the weavers were shown moderate levels. Finally, results have been discussed in detail by giving probable reasons experienced by the present investigators from where the sample has been drawn.

Key-Words: Weavers, Stressors, Predictors, Organizational Change, Madhubani, Bihar.

INTRODUCTION

Change is inevitable. Every moment everything is undergoing the process of change even human attitudes are also changing according to their needs and demands. Sometimes peoples are ready to accept change but some time resists accepting. It is due to lack of knowledge pertaining to outcomes of the changes. Hence, planned change is usually appreciated. In this fast developing society which is totally based on modern advanced technology and hi-info-tech as well where every organization try to compete each other in the consumer market by placing their good quality of product.

These days organizational change is necessary to understand the nature of shift which undergoing the process of change in this 21st century. Undoubtedly, we are shifting from industrial society to information society, forced technology to high-tech, national economy to world economy, short term to long term, centralization to decentralization, institutional help to self-help and representative democracy to participatory democracy. These are some of the important salient features of this century. The world is never static. It is always changing. The technology changes, the values in the society change, the governmental policy and program change, so do the human behavior. Most of the time the changes are so slow and gradual that they are hardly perceptible but sometimes they are so radical and sudden that we are left breathless. Sudden changes in recent years such as the policy of privatization, entry of multinational in the country and the liberal approach towards economy are bound to influence cognitively as well as conatively. It is our solemn duty as the man of organizational behavior to visualize the impact of such changes on behavior and devise ways and means to prepare people to adjust to the changes. Young men and women have recently been aspiring to seek employment in government organization because of greater job security. Recent trends point towards greater competitiveness and ample opportunities of absorption in private organizations. Capabilities instead of influence, competency instead of approachability, job commitment just sticking to the job will be the order of the day. People would be judged on the basis of excellent performance and the very meaning of excellence would be changed. The attitude of acquiring degrees may not be a valid passport for employment. Development of skill demanded by the job will assume precedence over the degree.

Organizational change

A number of definitions of organizational change draw attention to its convergent nature, it may bring re-structuring of the organization, change in technology, diversification of organization or its products, etc. if organizations do not incorporate the impact of organizational output in their structure, then very soon they may have to undergo another structural change. Organizational structural change might come into focus in establishing responsibilities, allocating tasks, defining communication and improving control systems. On the basis of past researches Ahmad (1994) pointed out that organizational change, today, encompasses all round change in technological, financial, material and in the potential human resources which have been witnessed from the contention of Leavitt (1964) who emphasized that organization can be changed by altering its structure, its technology and/or its people.

It is also pertinent to point out that change and human attitudes are closely related because attitudes are important when any change is brought into the organization, then how change will affect one's need and satisfaction in the organization. The reaction to change may be exhibited in the following forms:

- (i). Acceptance: If an individual perceives that the change will affect him favorably, he accepts it.

(ii). Resistance: If the individual employee feels that the change will affect him unfavorably, he resists it. Resistance to change becomes more forceful when the person concerned has a feeling that through resistance he may eliminate the change.

(iii). Indifference: Sometimes people fail to realize the impact of change or they feel that they will not be affected by the change, either way they remain indifferent.

(iv). Forced acceptance: Sometimes people are forced to accept the change, though they may resist it at initial stages but when change forces overpower resistance forces people have to accept it.

Apart from the above mentioned text, it is also important to point out that feelings are the part of each man's personal make-up and cannot be judged by human attitudes and their reaction to change. Generally people have a tendency to resist changes, so, planned change is brought by every organization because in planned change every one gets ample opportunity to go by with the demands of change to serve the organization better.

Any change causes stress. Hence, the present piece of research work is aimed to find out the weaver's occupational stressors as predictors of organizational change.

The term 'stress' comes from Latin literature; it was first used in English during 17th century. The term means distress, oppressions, and hardships. During the 18th and 19th century the meaning of stress shifted to natural sciences and engineering to represent force, pressure or strain, and or strong influence acting on a physical object or person which an individual resists in an attempt to maintain his original state.

Bridge Water and Sherwood (1956) have indicated in the Columbia Encyclopedia, stress is the internal force exerted by one part of a body upon the adjoining part, while strain is the deformation or change in dimension occasioned by stress. When body is subjected to pull it is said to be under tension, and when it is being pushed, i.e., is supporting a weight, it is under compressive stress. Shearing stress results from a force tending to make part of the body or one side of a plane slide past the other. Tensional stress occurs when external forces tend to twist a body around an axis.

Stress has become a part of life. Nowadays, everyone seems to be talking about stress. We also hear it not only in daily conversation but also through television, radio, the newspapers, conferences, stress centers, and university courses devoted to the topic. Remarkably, few people define the concept the same way and hardly bother to attempt for a clear-cut definition. In general, stress occurs when biological and physiological needs, as well as external demands and pressures are greater than the ability of the individual to adapt. According to Basowitz, et. al. (1955) stressful situations do not always produce responses in individuals. In the light of this

view Panchanathan and Shanmugaganesan (1992) have inferred that stress is a reaction to something that is happening to an individual. Moreover, it is one's way of coping with environment and threatening situations that he faces daily.

Seley (1956) in his pioneering work used the concept of stress in a manner relevant in social sciences. Seley expounded his biological concept of stress as the 'General Adaptation Syndrome' (GAS):- a three phase response to stress that begins with an alarm, continues with resistance, and terminates with exhaustion. This three phase response to stress incorporates the orchestrated set of physical and chemical changes which prepare an individual to fight or flee. This fight or flight label grows out of an evolutionary analysis of the origins of the stress response when our cave dwelling ancestors had only two options for dealing with the stress or "fight or flight response". The major concerns of our ancestors were found protecting themselves from environmental hazards and wild animals. It is a centuries old programmed-response to threat that is a master piece of survival engineering, and yet is tragically flawed in the sense that while the human nervous system is still responding the same way to environmental stressors, the stressors are not the same and the environment is radically different. The present day world abounds with uncertainties, which include natural calamities as well as unpredictable events and incidents.

It has been, in all times, a universal truth that the world is changing which is very much evident in the present era. Thus, the change and its effects have become the dominant features as the various authors have written on the Age of discontinuity (Drucker, 1968), the Age of Uncertainty (Galbraith, 1977) and the Age of Anxiety (Albrecht, 1979). However, the change is a continuous process which in itself is a great stressor in human life. In view of Lazarus (1966) stress is a universal human and animal phenomenon.

A review of definition on stress reveals that stress has been one of the important aspects that everyone has experienced but few could define, Lazarus (1966) stated that stress results in intense and distressing experience that appears to have tremendous influence on behavior.

Apart from the above context, it is to be mentioned here that stress is the general term applied to the pressures people feel in life. The presence of stress at work is almost inevitable in many jobs. However, individual differences account for a wide range of reactions to stress; a task viewed as challenging by one person may produce high level of anxiety in another. When a pressure begins to build up, it can cause adverse strain on a person's emotions, thought processes, and physical condition. When stress becomes excessive employees develop various symptoms of stress that can harm their job performance and health and even threaten their ability to cope with the environment. The people who are stressed may become nervous and chronically worried. They are easily provoked to anger and are unable to relax. They may be uncooperative or use alcohol or other drugs excessively. Although these conditions also occur from other causes, they are common symptoms of underlying stress.

Topper (2007) defines stress as a person's psychological and physiological response to the perception of demand and challenge. Nelson and Quick (1994) for example posit that stress is one of the most creatively ambiguous words, with as many interpretations as there are people who use the word, as even the experts do not agree on its definition. While Rees and Redfern (2000) assert that there is no universally accepted definition of the term stress, Ornelas and Kleiner (2003) argue that stress is the by-product of modern life that results from our efforts of trying to balance the demands of the workplace and of family life.

Scores of studies have been conducted on the phenomenon of stress and viewed many causes. There are many causes of stress in an organization, but many researchers argued that the main cause of occupational stress is work overload (Topper, 2007; Buchanan and Kaczenski, 2004). The increase in the work load in the organization without taking into account the availability of staff to carry out the tasks, may lead to occupational stress. Therefore, the work load increase in any organization should correspond with the availability of work force. Moreover, Buchanan and Huczynski (2004) also listed some typical causes of stress in an organizational setting as inadequate physical working environment, inappropriate job design, poor management style, poor relationships, uncertain future and divided loyalties.

In addition to above mentioned studies, Harvey and Brown (2006) for instance argued that the major stressors in the workplace includes changes in technology, downsizing, sudden reorganization and unexpected changes in the work schedules, competition for promotional opportunities, lack of participation in the decision making, and lack of employee empowerment. Others are conflicts with other employees at the work place, inadequate time to accomplish tasks, and violence in the workplace. The issue of acts of violence in the work place committed by both employees and customers contributes a lot to the employees' stress level. The negative effects of occupational stress are reduced efficiency, decreased capacity to perform, dampened initiative and reduced interest in working, increased rigidity of thought, lack of concern for the organization and colleagues and a loss of responsibility (Greenberg and Baron, 2000; Ivancevich, Matterson, Freedman and Philips, 1990).

Occupational stress contributes to low motivation and morale, decrease in performance, high turnover, sick leave, accidents, low job satisfaction, low quality products and services, poor internal communication and conflicts (Schabracq and Cooper 2000; Murphy, 1995; McHugh, 1993).

OBJECTIVES OF THE PRESENT STUDY:

A large number of studies on occupational stress and its stressors in relation to different psycho-social and organizational aspects have been studied (Ahmad, 2010; Pestonjee & Singh, 1982;

Pareek, 1983; Maddi and Kobasa, 1984; Misra & Singh, 1987; Dharmangadan, 1988) but very negligible number of studies in relation to organizational change has been found in Indian context. The sample undertaken for the present investigation is of utmost value and still has not been studied with particular reference to weavers working in Madhubani district of North Bihar. It is important to be mentioned that Madhubani is centuries old art and is done by mainly the females of the family in addition to house-hold works. Madhubani weavers took advantage of the humid conditions prevailing because of the proximity to the Kosi River. Moreover being under the slopes of the hill ranges of Nepal, helped them acuminate their cotton spinning skills to a great extent that hard spun – hard woven cotton ‘mulmuls’ of Madhubani became as renowned as the paintings of the region. In Madhubani, the cotton fabrics are still very much in demand by the true lovers of excellent cotton. Madhubani Weavers near the capital of the state, Patna, never lagged behind in the pursuit of fine exposition of their skills. They came up with exceptional dress materials as well as furnishing materials, whose designs have not stagnated but they have emerged with time. Thus, the present study was aimed at studying the occupational stress and its stressors among weavers working in different locality of Madhubani district of North Bihar. No doubt, the present study will fill the void of knowledge in the area chosen by present investigators and the whole study will help in making congenial environment within weavers’ community working in Madhubani district.

HYPOTHESES:

On the basis of the broad objectives of the present study the following hypothesis were formulated;

- a. None of the dimensions/stressors of occupational stress will predict the weavers perceived reactions to organizational change
- b. Most of the weavers especially in Madhubani district will show higher degree of acceptability towards perceived organizational change.

METHODOLOGY:

Sample: In carrying out the present piece of research work, total weavers N=100 selected from different localities of Madhubani district where the most of weavers were engaged in manufacturing cotton cloths for using kurta, saree, dhoti, trouser, towels, etc.

Tool Used: In order to achieve the objective of the present piece of research work the following tools were used for collecting the data:

1. **ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE SCALE:** For the measuring weavers’ perceived reactions towards organizational change, a scale developed by **Rahman and Akhtar (1991)** was used. The scale consisted of 25 items and the subjects were required to give responses to the items on a 5- point scale ranging from “Strongly Agree” to “Strongly

Disagree”. The reported split-half reliability of the scale is $r=.85$ which confirms the reliability of organizational change scale.

2. **OCCUPATIONAL STRESS INDEX (OSI):** For measuring weavers’ occupational stress, as well as, the dimensions of occupational stress index, an OSI developed by **Srivastava and Singh (1981)** was used. OSI consisted of 46 items covering 12 dimensions of occupational stress (Appendix-2). These dimensions have been stated by the authors as sub-scales (or occupational stressors) are - (1) role overload, (2) role ambiguity, (3) role conflict, (4) unreasonable group and political pressures, (5) responsibility for persons, (6) under participation, (7) powerlessness, (8) poor peer-relations, (9) intrinsic impoverishment, (10) low status, (11) strenuous working conditions, and (12) unprofitability. Covering 12 – sub-dimensions as stressors, in all, occupational stress index consisted of 46 items as stated above which had to be rated on a 5-point scale “ranging from” strongly agree to strongly disagree out of 46 items, 28 are true-keyed items and the remaining 18 items are false-keyed items. The reported split-half reliability of the scale is .94, hence, it confirms the efficacy of the scale.
3. **BIOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION BLANK (BIB):-** For taping information regarding the respondents biographies, a “Biographical Information Blank” (BIB) was also prepared that included age, marital status, Income, qualification, total experience (in years), and number of dependents and the respondents were requested to furnish this information.

PROCEDURES:

The above three test materials viz., organizational change scale, occupational stress index and, biographical information blank were in printed form and were administered individually on all the weavers working in around Madhubani district. All the weavers were also assured by taking in to confidence that provided information would be kept strictly confidential and would be used for research purposes only.

Having collected the responses to the items of the scales, they were scored according to the procedure and the individual scores were obtained. Finally scores were given statistical treatment and presented in tables. The obtained results were discussed and the formulated hypotheses were tested.

STATISTICAL ANALYSES:

In this study, standard multiple regressions out of various multiple regressions have been used as this analysis through computer was made available. This strategy allows all independent variables to get inter simultaneously into the regression equation. Each independent variable is evaluated in terms of what it adds to go prediction on the dependent variable.

Apart from regression analysis, Q1 and Q3 were also calculated to obtain the groups, differing in levels of their perceived reactions to organizational change.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

In quest of investigating the percentages of Weavers' reactions towards organizational change, it is apparently clear from the table- 1 which reveals that only 19 percent of the weavers working in Madhubani district have shown high acceptability reactions towards organizational change.

Table – 1 Showing Extent of Weavers' Perceived Reactions towards Organizational Change (OC)

Levels	N=100	Percentage
Low	33	33
Moderate	48	48
High	19	19

Mean value of organizational change = 87.61

It can be seen from the Table – 1 that out of 100 weavers, very large number of weavers i.e. 48.00 percent has shown moderate, whereas, 33 percent of the group has shown low but favorable acceptability to change. The result presented above can also be observed by the following pie chart.

When the data of weavers were analyzed by analysis of variance for the regression statistics then, it has been found that independent variables have significant predictive influence for weavers' reactions towards organizational change as given obtained F-value 2.3313 in Table – 2 is significant at .05 level of confidence. The result confirms the rejection of the proposed hypothesis that none of the stressors of occupational stress and Biographical variables will emerge as the predictors of organizational change.

Table – 2: Analysis of Variance for Regression of Weavers

Source of variation	df	Sum of squares	Mean squares	F. value
Attributable to Regression	17	582.93144	52.54282	2.3313*
Deviation from Regression	82	586.25437	18.94786	
Total	99	1158.2163		

* Significant at .05 level

Table – 3 depicts the real predictor of organizational change for the group of weavers' community working in Madhubani district of North Bihar which could be observed from the table given below:

Table – 3 Multiple Regression Analysis for Weavers

Sl. No.	Variables	Value of "r"	Regression coefficient	Std. Error of regression coefficient	t-value
1	Role overload	-0.01383	3.12501	1.85685	1.60453
2	Role ambiguity	-0.13708	3.44230	2.13300	1.64636
3	Role conflict	-0.22171	2.80925	2.07040	1.41708
4	Unreasonable group & political pressure	-0.02553	3.33746	1.86107	1.60651
5	Responsibility for persons	-0.11467	4.10611	2.11625	1.73301
6	Under participation	-0.17312	2.34141	.09055	1.10032
7	Powerlessness	-0.18131	3.96282	2.03606	2.28656*
8	Poor peer-relations	-0.14126	3.46051	1.82442	1.80241
9	Intrinsic impoverishment	-0.38543	2.42370	2.1636	1.63341
10	Low status	-0.35760	3.37301	2.7148	2.31136*
11	Strenuous working conditions	-0.41778	-3.3126	2.11811	0.96870
12	Unprofitability	0.41578	-3.31277	2.01811	1.63054
13	Total occupational stress	0.20239	0.64112	0.48296	1.30014
14	Age	0.12935	-1.12375	1.01312	1.10818
15	Total experience	0.01207	-1.40338	0.78231	1.78523
16	Experience in the present position	0.12839	-1.00699	0.94875	1.18662
17	Income	0.13396	1.13805	2.00572	2.23642*

Dependent: Organizational change
 Mean: 87.61
 SD: 5.65785
 Intercept: 79.86528
 Multiple correlations: 0.70604
 Standard Error of Estimate: 4.78144
 Note: * Significant at .05 levels

It is important to be mentioned that only two dimensions/ stressors of Occupational Stress Index i.e., "powerlessness" and "Low Status", in fact, a real predictors to the weavers' reactions towards organizational change have been found as its t-values 2.2865 and 2.31136 have been found significant at .05 level of confidence respectively. Moreover, "Income" as one of the biographical variables have been found important predictor towards weavers' reactions to change as t – value 2.23642 was found to be significant at 0.05 level of confidence especially from where the present sample has been drawn.

The above mentioned results seem to be quite logical that weavers of Madhubani district have shown relatively occupational stress towards the degree of perceived reactions to change. There may be various reasons such as inadequate supply of materials concerning to products and other facilities such as designing, coloring, etc from the state government in general and central government in particular. Although, it is important to be mentioned that the researchers, behaviorists and other social scientists are always engaged in searching the problems related to organizations. As it is often seen that most of the organizations changes brought up in to their organization so far as policies, technology and people are concerned. This is the result of economic globalization but by implementing changes management always faces a lot of psychological problems. There may be some important issues or factors while introducing change in the organization, before implementing any change in to the organization, the outcome of the changes must be clarified among the weavers so, it seems that these may have impact on organizational change. Thus, two stressors of occupational stress, namely, 'powerlessness' and 'low status' and one biographical variable 'income' have been emerged as the most important predictors of organizational change especially among Madhubani weavers.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS:

In the light of the obtained results and its interpretations the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Two important stressors of occupational stress, viz. 'Powerlessness, and 'Low Status' have been found as the predictors of organizational change especially from where the present research has been carried out.
2. One of the most important biographical variables, namely, 'Income' has also been found as the predictors which influences the organizational change.
3. Very meager number of weavers of Madhubani district has shown higher degree of acceptability towards organizational change i.e. 19 percent only.
4. On the basis of observations experienced by the present investigators have revealed the fact that the present era, every moment, every organization is undergoing the process of change; some are in a constant way and others slowly and gradually. But it is observed that planned change especially in Madhubani district is needed for the promotion of weavers. Hence, it is suggested that Indian researcher especially organizational behavior people must look in to the fact as they have almost neglected the study on organizational change in relation to some other important psycho-social dimensions for the promotion of

weavers' community, although, they have contributed a lot for our nation's building by using hand looms. Moreover, our state and union government must provide all necessities for the promotion of hand loom cotton industries by which our youth can get self – employment for their best survival on earth.

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1. **Powerlessness:** A situation in which authority given does not commensurate with the responsibilities of the Job.

Low Status: A state of insignificance in the organizational network as well as in the social system